

CIVIL PROCEDURE: TASKS, FUNCTIONS, PROCEDURAL FORM

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the main objectives, functions, and features of the procedural form of civil proceedings in the Republic of Uzbekistan. It provides a comprehensive analysis of the role of civil proceedings in ensuring the realization and protection of the subjective rights and legitimate interests of citizens, organizations, and the state. It explores the key objectives of civil procedure, including ensuring fairness, legality, access to justice, as well as restoring violated rights and preventing offenses in the civil sphere.

Keywords: civil procedure, procedural form, objectives, functions, justice, violated rights.

Civil procedure in the Republic of Uzbekistan is a vital instrument for implementing the principles of the rule of law and ensuring the rule of law. It regulates the consideration and resolution of disputes arising from civil, family, labor, housing, and other legal relationships, protecting the rights and legitimate interests of citizens, organizations, and the state.

Uzbekistan's current judicial and legal policy is aimed at strengthening the independence of the courts, increasing the efficiency of legal proceedings, and ensuring access to justice for every citizen. The primary goal of civil proceedings is the fair, comprehensive, and timely consideration of cases¹. Judicial activity must ensure the protection of the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of all parties involved, as well as contribute to strengthening the rule of law and public order. Civil proceedings realize citizens' constitutional right to judicial protection, making them a key element of a democratic system of governance.

The objectives of civil procedure reflect its social and legal significance. One of the main objectives of civil procedure is to ensure effective judicial protection of the personal, political, economic, and social rights of citizens, as well as the interests of the state and organizations². Judicial bodies must guarantee the restoration of violated rights, the elimination of legal uncertainty, and the fair resolution of conflicts. The consideration of civil cases fosters respect for the law and justice in society. Fair court decisions ensure uniform application of the law and strengthen public trust in the judicial system³.

¹ Хабибуллаев Д. Суд-ҳуқуқ ислохотлари шароитида фуқаролик процессуал қонунчилигини такомиллаштиришнинг долзарб масалалари //Обзор законодательства Узбекистана. – 2013. – №. 1. – С. 5-8.

² ХАБИБУЛЛАЕВ Д. SOME IDEAS ON THE IMPROVEMENT OF CIVIL PROCEDURAL CODE OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN //Юридик фанлар ахборотномаси. – 2017. – №. 1. – С. 75-79.

³ https://op.raj.ru/pdf/grazhd_process.pdf

In addition, civil procedure fulfills an important social function: it helps resolve disputes peacefully and legally at the level of the law, preventing them from escalating into acute social contradictions⁴. This is particularly important for strengthening stability and harmony in the multi-ethnic society of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Modern dispute resolution and fair adjudication play a preventative role, preventing repeated or similar rights violations in the future.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, civil proceedings occupy an important place in the system of protecting the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of citizens, organizations, and the state. The objectives of civil procedure are realized through the performance of such functions as restorative, preventative, cautionary, and educational⁵.

The law-restoration function is expressed in the restoration of violated or disputed rights and freedoms of citizens, as well as in ensuring the protection of the interests of organizations.

Preventive and warning functions contribute to the prevention of new offenses, since fair and timely consideration of cases has a disciplinary effect on participants in civil proceedings.

The educational function is manifested in the development of a sense of justice, legal awareness, and respect for the judicial system in citizens.

It should also be noted that, in accordance with the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, civil proceedings are divided into several types. These include: claim proceedings, writ proceedings, proceedings in cases arising from public law relations, and special proceedings⁶.

Each of these types has its own characteristics, case processing procedure, and legal consequences.

Claim proceedings are the most common form of protecting violated rights and presuppose a dispute between the parties.

Order proceedings are used in cases where the claim is indisputable and supported by adequate evidence, which allows for the expedited protection of rights.

Proceedings in cases arising from public law relations regulate disputes between individuals, organizations, and government agencies when it comes to protecting rights in the sphere of management⁷.

Special proceedings, in turn, are used in situations where there is no dispute over law, and the court merely needs to establish a legal fact or confirm a specific right.

Thus, civil proceedings in the Republic of Uzbekistan represent a complex yet harmonious system that ensures effective judicial protection and contributes to strengthening the legal culture of society.

Regarding the procedural form, in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the civil procedural form represents a legally established, streamlined, and optimal procedure for administering justice in civil

⁴ Ибратова Ф. Б. и др. СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ НЕКОТОРЫХ МЕР ПРОЦЕССУАЛЬНОГО ПРИНУЖДЕНИЯ В СФЕРЕ ГРАЖДАНСКО-ПРОЦЕССУАЛЬНОГО ПРАВА //International journal of professional science. – 2022. – №. 10-2. – С. 5-16.

⁵ Янбиволев Н. ФУҚАРОЛИК СУД ИШЛАРИНИ ЮРИТИШДА ТАФТИШ ИНСТАНЦИЯСИНИНГ ЎРНИ //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 12. – С. 1146-1151.

⁶ Хорев, А. А., & Эриашвили, Н. Д. (2013). Гражданский процесс: задачи, функции, процессуальная форма. Вестник Московского университета МВД России, (3), 149-150

⁷ Идибоев А. ФУҚАРОЛИК ПРОЦЕССИДА ШАРТНОМА БЎЙИЧА (ИХТИЁРИЙ) ВАКИЛЛИК ҚИЛИШНИНГ ҲУҚУҚИЙ АСОСЛАРИ //Наука и научный потенциал: основа устойчивого инновационного развития общества. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 49-56.

cases. This procedure is aimed at ensuring the legality, fairness, and uniformity of judicial practice⁸. The obligation to comply with the civil procedural form is guaranteed by the measures of responsibility provided for by the norms of the Civil Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other legal norms⁹.

In other words, the civil procedural form in the Republic of Uzbekistan serves as a legal mechanism that determines the sequence of actions of the court and participants in the process when considering civil cases, ensuring their transparency, objectivity and protection of all parties¹⁰.

The civil procedural form is regulated in detail by the Civil Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which enshrines the principles of legal proceedings, the procedure for filing applications, the rights and obligations of participants in the process, as well as the mechanism for executing court decisions¹¹.

The civil procedural system in the Republic of Uzbekistan has a number of key characteristics: Detailed regulation by law. All stages of civil proceedings – from filing a claim to enforcing a court decision – are strictly governed by procedural rules, eliminating arbitrary interpretation and ensuring uniformity in judicial practice¹².

Universality. It applies at all stages of civil case proceedings, regardless of their category and the nature of the dispute.

Defining the circle of participants. The procedural form establishes who may participate in the case: the parties (plaintiff and defendant), third parties, representatives, as well as other participants in the proceedings: witnesses, experts, specialists, translators, and others¹³.

Observance of procedural rules is mandatory. Failure to comply with established requirements entails adverse consequences for the parties involved, such as dismissal of the application, imposition of a fine, or reversal of the court decision¹⁴.

Moreover, scholars and practitioners often highlight additional characteristics of the civil procedural form, such as normativity, continuity, and systematicity, which reflect its internal logic and the interconnectedness of all stages of legal proceedings.

The civil procedural form is of great theoretical and practical importance for the judicial system of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It ensures orderliness, consistency, and transparency of judicial proceedings, serving as an integral element of the constitutional principle of the administration of justice. Adherence to the procedural form guarantees the protection of the rights of citizens and organizations, and is an important condition for strengthening public trust in the courts and the law.

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⁹ Юридическая процессуальная форма. Теория и практика. М.,1976 С.179.

¹⁰ Аллаёров Ж. Место международного гражданского процесса в международном частном праве //Обзор законодательства Узбекистана. – 2020. – №. 2. – С. 63-67.

¹¹ Мамасиддиқов М. М. Фуқаролик процесси: ўқув қўлланма. – 2014.

¹² Саттаров Ф. Общие положения представительства в гражданском процессе //Инновационные подходы к современной науке. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 25-29.

¹³ Бебутова З. Ф. ФУҚАРОЛИК СУД ИШЛАРИНИ ЮРИТИШДА АДВОКАТНИНГ ВАЗИФАЛАРИ //Студенческий вестник. – 2021. – №. 17-8. – С. 53-56.

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